

**EXPRESSION OF NUMERATIVES IN PHRASEOLOGY IN THE
TURKIC LANGUAGES** (*Uzbek, Kazakh and Karakalpak languages*)

PhD. **Ismailov Gulom Mirzaevich**

Associate Professor of Alfraganus University in Tashkent

ABSTRACT

This article studies the unique embodiment of numbers in phraseologisms in Turkic languages, namely Uzbek, Kazakh and Karakalpak. It is also found out on the basis of examples that numbers in phraseologisms have formed different concepts in different linguistic cultures.

Keywords: phraseologism, Turkic languages, number, time, wholeness, seme, meaning, religio-mythological cognitive structure.

Phraseology requires knowledge of the life and history of a certain people, fluent possession of linguistic realities, and is also associated with the traditions, culture, religion and psychological characteristics of the speakers of a particular language [1, p. 6]. Therefore, phraseologisms are a product of the accumulated life experience of a certain people over the centuries, national traditions and customs, are formed in certain periods and reflect the socio-political lifestyle of that period.

Most phraseological units are formed on the basis of events related to human life, spiritual and physical state, and *zoologisms*, *somatisms*, mythological phenomena, colors and numbers in their composition serve as the semantic base components of phraseological units. Phraseological units with a number component are also actively used in a certain amount in Turkic languages. Numbers are absorbed into the structure of any culture and organize the information in it into content groups. This situation ensures the transmission of knowledge from generation to generation, regardless of the presence or absence of a written or oral

tradition in this culture. In Turkic languages, numbers form phraseological units as a logical basis, and these numbers, embodying religious-mythological and cultural-ethnic features, correspond to the national culture, customs and traditions of the representatives of this language. “Along with other stable associations in the folk language, our language contains many phraseological units, including phraseological units with numbers, expressing the bright national characteristics of the language, giving it a special playfulness” [4].

In linguistic cognitive research, knowledge, which reflects culture in language, is a specific object. Knowledge is the basis of cognitive construction, which is the result of the reflection of existing signs and properties in the human mind. Elements of knowledge, as a rule, are collected in a specific complex, mental system, knowledge or cognitive structure, which in various forms has recently been called a frame. The issue of the frame is found in works on cognitive psychology or artificial intelligence [6, p. 3-9], as well as in studies on cognitive linguistics [11, p. 52-92]. According to Ch.Fillmor, the frame model is a model of semantics of understanding. This model allows for a complete, detailed understanding of the information-content that the speaker intends and the listener sees. As is known, numbers reflect the specific religious, mythological and cultural characteristics of a particular people. Therefore, in the process of observation, the religio-mythological cognitive structure of phraseologisms formed on the basis of numbers in Turkic languages is manifested in "phraseological frames" with the following general characteristics. Here are a few of these to prove our point:

I. “wholeness”.

The word *bir* (one) symbolizes wholeness, existence, and the beginning and end of counting. The formation of numbers in such a frame is expressed in the following phraseologisms in the Uzbek, Kazakh, and Karakalpak languages. For example:

In Uzbek: *Bir yostiqqa bosh qo‘ymoq* (O‘TIL, 1, 335) Zaynab ham umid bilan bir yostiqqa bosh qo‘ygan. (A.Qodiriy, O‘tgan kunlar).

in Kazakh: *бір түндік астында түтін түтетмі* (ФС, 75). *Бырақ арғы жағынан бір-біріне қанша құштар боп ынтығып тұрса да ендігі жерде баяғыдай бір түндік астында бас құрап, түтін түтетіп туру – бұларға бұйырмақ емес.*

in Karakalpak: *Bir dastiqqa bas qoydı* (QTF, 26).

These examples show that in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages, phraseological units expressing the “wholeness” frame were formed by transferring the meanings of free conjunctions. Whatever the meanings of free conjunctions, phraseological units formed through imagery retained a certain characteristic. In the Kazakh language, phraseological units formed phraseological meaning on the basis of spontaneity.

II. "conflict", "danger".

The word *ikki* (two), on the other hand, goes back to dualism, a philosophical doctrine that considers the world to be fundamentally composed of matter and spirit. Concepts such as inequality and contradiction are expressed in the following phraseological units with the participation of this numeral:

in Uzbek: *ikki orada qolmoq* (O‘TIL, 112). O‘g‘ilning jilovini bo‘sh qo‘yib yubordingiz. Ikki o‘rtada qizim badnom bo‘lib qoldi (S.Ahmad, Qadrdon dalalar).

in Kazakh: *екі оттын арасында қалу (екі түйе сүйкенсе, ортасында шыбын өледі)* (ҚОФС, 64). *Соңғы жылдары кілең екі оттың арасында, ұстараның жүзінде өмір сүрді зой марқұм (“Дарабоз”).*

in Karakalpak: *eki ottıń arasında qaldı* (ҚТФ, 35).

Both components (two, grass) used in these phraseology show the commonality of mutual religious-mythological worldviews of the Turkic peoples.

III. “waiting”, “longing”.

The word *to‘rt* (four) is symbolic of the four directions of the world and the four elements (fire, water, air, earth).

in Uzbek: *ko‘zi to‘rt bo‘lmoq* (Sh.Rahmatullaevdan). *Necha yillar yelib o‘tda oradan, //Ota-ona kutib ko‘zi to‘rt bo‘ldi* (D.Do‘st, Yurt qadri).

in Kazakh: *төрт көзи түгел* (ФС, 689). *...аяулы халықтың өз мемлекеттігінің 2500 жылдығын тойлайтын уақыты жақын шығар деп шеттегі бауырларымыз үлкен үмітпен қарап, сол күнді төрт көзи түгел күтуде* (Егемен Қазақстан, №379-380, 2009).

in Karakalpak: *eki kózi tórt boldı* (ҚТФ, 35). *...май заводының дийуалына сүйенип мени күтип тұрған тулғаси тап ҳәзиргидей өлмегендей тири болып еки көзи төрт болып мени күтип тұрғаны көз алдымда турады-ау!* (Г.Е.).

IV. “alienation”, “joy”.

The word *yetti* (seven) can be included in the cultural concepts of the Uzbek, Kazakh, and Karakalpak peoples. This number can have different meanings in different peoples. For example, “in English, the number seven represents such meanings as harmony and order (rule, method)” [10, p. 10]. In general, the number seven as a religious concept represents a symbol of universality, that is, spiritual perfection, that is, “seven is the unifier of the earthly four and the heavenly three” [3]. Turkic peoples have associated various religious and natural phenomena in life with this number: these are concepts such as seven days, seven miracles, seven treasures, seven generations, seven climates, seven colors, seven planets, the seventh heaven, and seven obligations. It should be emphasized that since ancient times, the number seven has had a special significance and is mainly associated with religion, religious ceremonies, and folk customs. It is noted that among the Turkic peoples, the structure of the world is expressed by the number seven [8, p. 13], that is, seven layers of the earth, seven heavens. More precisely, the seven layers of the earth include the central core, the outer liquid part of the core, the

mantle, the basalt layer, the granite layer, the hydrosphere, and the atmosphere. In addition, in our galaxy, there are seven layers, one above the other, starting from the Earth and moving away from the Sun, the passage of seven planets, the concept of “seven layers of heaven” has become figuratively generalized in the human mind and has begun to be applied to a specific phenomenon.

Based on this idea, phraseological units related to the concept of *yetti* (seven) in Turkic languages can be divided into the following phraseological groups. Among Turkic peoples, seven has the meaning of “border”, “boundary”, the number seven also expresses a kinship relationship, that is, humanity must know its seven fathers (ancestors), and anyone after seven is considered a stranger [8, p. 14]. Therefore, the following phraseological units were formed based on the semantic meaning "stranger" of the number seven:

The Uzbek language uses the phraseology of *yeti yot begona*. In the sacred books, it is said that the good and bad of each person go to seven generations. Children from the same father are considered relatives up to the seventh generation, that is, parents, children, grandchildren, great-grandchildren (*ota-ona, farzandlar, nevara, chevara, evara, dubora, novora*). *O‘z uyidan boshqa yurtga, yetti yot begona odamlar orasiga surgun qilinish qanday bo‘lishini tasavvur qiling-a!* (*Dovuyurak inson. Hikoya*). In Kazakh *жеті атасын білмеген мұрт (құл)* (ФС, 263). *жеті атасын билмеген діннен шыққан, тексіз құл...* (ФС). *жеті ата жау* (ФС, 263). *Бирде тату, бирде араз құбылма дос, // Досым түгіл жеті ата жаудан жаман* (Б.Күлеев), *жеті дуспан* (ФС, 263). *Бұл айел – жеті дуспанның бірі* (А.Нұрпейісов). *жеті жининен беттер көриу* (КТФ, 44).

Phraseologisms with the mean "joy": *yettinchi falakda suzmoq*. “*Men dunyodagi eng baxtli ayolman!*” – *deb mag‘rurlandi. shunday kezlari oyog‘i yerdan uzilib, yettinchi falakda suzib yurgandek sezardi o‘zini* (F.Tilovat, *Qora quzg‘un*); In Kazakh *жерден жеті қоян тапқандай* (ФС, 259). ...хатшысы Саян Хамитжанов ұлттық құраманың тізгінін ұстаған чех маманын “орыс

тілін жақсы меңгерген” деп жерден жеті қоян тапқандай қуанды (Alaman.kz); In Karakalpak *жерден жеті қоян тапқандай болуы*. [2, p. 80].

Phraseologisms representing the mean of "time": *Yetti kecha, yetti kunduz to‘y bermoq. Yetti kecha, yetti kunduz tinimsiz to‘y-to‘ylasharkan. Жеті түнде* (ҚТҚФС, 80). *Ашыу үстінде абайламаған еді, жаңа сезип, басын шайқады, жеті түнде ашыу қысты* (Ғ.Айжанов) [9, p. 74]; *жеті қаранғы түн* (ФС, 264). *Сол ағамыз кей кездері жеті қаранғы түнде орынынан тұрып, он-жйрма шұмақ өлеңді дайындықсыз-ақ жазып тастайды-ғой* (Жүңго қазақ радё торабы). The use of the number yetti (seven) in these phraseological units also has a unique symbolic meaning.

It should be noted that the figurative expression of certain events in society, based on cosmological and religious-mythological ideas about the creation of the world and the seven layers of Heaven and Earth, in the minds of representatives of certain languages, served as the basis for the emergence of numerous phraseological units.

V. “time”.

The word *qirq* (forty), as written in religious sources, is a symbol of purification, that is, the soul leaves a person forty days after his death. Kazakh linguist S. Kenesbaev writes about the active participation of this number in the genesis of the Turkic peoples, its difference from other numbers [5, p. 23]. Religious and mythological concepts such as forty nights, forty days, forty verses, forty hadiths can serve as a vivid example of this. It should be said that this number is mainly associated with the religious and mythological worldview of the Turkic peoples. “Based on the people's ideas about supernatural forces, images of witches, forty thieves or robbers, who have the magical power of the number forty, arose. In addition, the number forty is also considered a period of growth, preparation and maturation. "Forty days of preparation for a particular event, forty days of feasting and entertainment, forty days of heroic sleep, etc. are based on the magical power

of this number" [7, p. 152]. It is clear that the internal structure of phraseological units is a mirror of cultural information.

in Uzbek: *qirqini o'tkazmoq. Onasining janozasi, yigirmasi, qirqi,xatmi qur'on deb ancha chiqimdor bo'lganga o'xshadi (S.Anorboev, Mehr).*

in Kazakh: *қырқыннан шықты. Балам қырқыннан шығып, қарын шашы алынғалы ұйқысы тынышталды (ФС, 493).*

in Karakalpak: *qırıq kún jol júerdi (ҚҚ халқ нақллари). Солаўқаттан күш алған Илияс Құдайдың таўы болған Хорёбу таўына шекем қырық күн, қырық түн жол жүрди.*

It is clear that there are differences in the content of phraseological units in Turkic languages. This situation is closely related to factors such as the natural living conditions, cultural and religious traditions of these peoples. Numbers participate in phraseological units as a semantic base component and a semantic non-base component, forming unique religious-mythological and cognitive landscapes based on five phraseological frames. These phraseological units also reflect the unique national-cultural and religious-mythological worldview of representatives of a particular language.

Reference

1. Баясгалан Ш. Семантика числительных во фразеологии монгольского, русского и английского языков. КД. СПб., 2006.
2. Ешбаев Ж. Қарақалпақ тилинің қысқаша фразеологиялық сөзлиги. – Нөкис: Каракалпакстан, 1985.
3. Значение чисел. <http://zagovor.by/numerology/3-page-3.html>
4. Исабеков И.Н. Фразеологизмы с количественными числительными. www.arch.kyrlibnet.kg/?&npage=download&nadd=774

5. Кенесбаев С.К. О некоторых особенностях фразеологических единиц в казахском языке // Известия АН Казахской ССР. Серия филология и искусствоведения. Вып.1-2. 1954.
6. Минский М. Фреймы для представления знаний / Пер. с англ. – М.: Энергия, 1979; Haselager W. Cognitive science and folk psychology: The right frame of mind. L.etc:Sage Publication, – London, 1977.
7. Мирзаева С. Ўзбек халқ романик дostonлари поэтикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2004.
8. Муратова Р.Т. Символика чисел в башкирском языке. АКД. – М., 2009.
9. Наўризбаева С.Т. Фразеологические единицы в каракалпакско-русском словаре. – Ташкент, 1972.
10. Рафисова Г.Л. Нумерологические фразеологические единицы в английском и татарском языках. АКД. – Уфа, 2004.
11. Филлмор Ч. Фреймы и семантика понимания // Новое в зарубежной лингвистике. – М.: Прогресс, 1988. Вып. 23. – С. 52-92.